

MODERN PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES AND THEIR ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN MOBILE APPLICATION AND WEB APPLICATION CREATION.

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Abstract: Mobile application (English: Mobile app) is a program designed for use on smartphones, tablets and other mobile devices developed for a specific platform (iOS, Android, Windows Phone, etc.). Most mobile applications come pre-installed on the device itself or can be downloaded for free or for a fee from online application stores such as the App Store, Google Play, etc. Initially, mobile applications were used to quickly check e-mail, but their high demand led to their expansion into other areas, such as mobile phone and GPS games, chatting, watching videos and using the Internet.

Keywords: Mobile App, Java, Android, Kotlin, Flutter, Dart, iOS, Android, React Native, Figma, programming languages.

The following programming languages are mainly used in mobile application development:[1,2,3,4]

Figure 1. Software used in mobile application development.

Java programming language is one of the best programming languages in which you can create enterprise-level products (programs). Many projects and applications, as well as large enterprise programs, are written in Java.[5,6,7,8,9] Java is a classic, strongly typed language and is therefore suitable for entry-level learners. This programming language is based on the Oak programming language. The Oak (meaning oak tree) programming language was started in the early 90s by Sun Microsystems (now operating under the name of Oracle) with the aim of creating a new generation of smart devices that work independently

of the platform (operating system). To achieve this, Sun people planned to use C++, but for some reason they gave up on this idea.[10,11,12,13,14,15]

Kotlin language is a young language. Although it has been around since 2011, it was only in May 2019 that Google announced it as the priority programming language for the Android platform, and given that Google is developing Android, Kotlin's popularity among developers has grown rapidly since this event. Following trends, many employers have started requiring Kotlin knowledge.

In addition to being recognized by Google, Kotlin's popularity in mobile development is due to its ease of use.

Flutter is an open source software development kit created by Google. It is used to develop Android, iOS, Windows, Mac, Linux, Google Fuchsia and web applications from a single codebase.[16,17,18,19,20,21,22]

The first version of Flutter was codenamed "Sky" and ran on the Android operating system. It was announced at the 2015 Dart Developer Summit, to be able to run at 120 frames per second. At the Google Developer Days keynote in Shanghai, Google announced Flutter Release Preview 2, the last major release before Flutter 1.0. On December 4, 2018, Flutter 1.0 was released at the Flutter Live event, marking the first "stable" version of the Framework. Flutter 1.12 was released on December 11, 2019 at the Flutter Interactive event.

Figure 2. Dart platform.

Dart Platform Flutter programs are written in Dart language and use advanced features of the language. Through the semi-official Flutter Desktop Embedded project, running on Windows, MacOS, and Linux, the Flutter Dart virtual machine has a concurrent execution engine. When writing and debugging an application, Flutter uses Just In Time compilation, which allows for "rebooting" by which changes can be made to a running application. Flutter supports this state for stateful hot reloading, in most cases changes made to the source code can be reflected immediately in the running application without requiring a restart or loss of any state.

Release versions of Flutter apps on Android and iOS are built with out-of-the-box (AOT) compilation, which ensures high performance of Flutter on mobile devices.[23,24,25,26,27,28]

React Native- is a library for developing applications for Android and IOS devices, based on the React Javascript library created by Facebook. React Native was developed by Facebook developers on March 26, 2015. Nowadays, many good software and applications are built using React Native. React Native is an easy-to-learn, widely used library for iOS, Android, and the Web.

Figure 3. Ionic framework(frame).

Ionic- an open-source mobile UI (User Interface) toolkit for creating modern mobile applications, from Rect, Vue, Angular in a single high-quality cross-platform open-source codebase.[29,30,31,32,33,34]

Figure 4. Vue Native Framework

Vue Native- A framework for creating cross-platform mobile applications using the JavaScript programming language.

Programming languages are very diverse, and each of them can be used to solve specific problems. Below we will get acquainted with information about the most famous of them.[35,36,37,38]

HTML programming language.

HTML is short for HyperText Markup Language and was developed by Tim Berners-Lee in 1990. HTML is used to create electronic documents (called pages) displayed on the WWW. Each page is connected to each other by "hyperlinks". Clicking on those links will take you to other pages. Every web page you see on the Internet is written using one version or another of HTML. The HTML code ensures that text and images are properly formatted so that your Internet browser displays them as intended.[39,40,41,42,43] Without HTML, the browser would not know how to display text as elements or load images. HTML also provides the basic structure of the page, which then changes the appearance of the Cascading Style Sheet.

JAVASCRIPT- a language for writing interactive web sites. JavaScript is a programming language used to make web pages interactive. It brings the page to life, creating interactive elements and animations that engage the user. If you've used the search box on the home page, or watched a video, it's probably running JavaScript. JavaScript and Java are two different computer languages, both developed in 1995. Java is an object-oriented programming language, which means it can run independently in a computer environment. JavaScript, on the other hand, is a text-based programming language designed to run as part of a web-based application.[44,45,46,47] Unlike Java programs, which must be built before running in a web-based environment, JavaScript is designed to be integrated into HTML. All major web browsers support JavaScript. The great thing about JavaScript is that you don't need to know how to write it to use it in your web code. You can find free JavaScripts online. The only thing you need to know to use such commands (codes) is how to place the provided code in the right places on your website. you don't need to know how to write it to use it in your web code. You can find free JavaScripts online. The only thing you need to

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PHP -language for creating dynamic websites. PHP Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) is a programming language that allows web developers to create dynamic content that interfaces with databases. PHP is mainly used for developing web-based applications. Rasmus Lerdorf released the first version of PHP in 1994. PHP is a recurring abbreviation for "PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor". PHP is a server-side scripting language embedded in HTML. It is used to create dynamic content management, databases, session tracking, even all e-commerce sites. It is integrated with popular databases such as MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, Sybase, Informix and Microsoft SQL Server.

FORTRAN-programming language. The oldest high-level programming language. A programming language for scientific calculations. FORTRAN (Formula Translator) was developed by John Backus in 1956 for IBM Corporation (International Business Machines). Arithmetic operations, common logical problems, list forms, economic calculations are easily performed in the language. Fortran language has been holding a strong place until now. Because it was originally designed for mathematical processing of data. After all, the main calculation algorithms in this field of human activity remain the same as they were 50 years ago. Two of the most popular versions of the FORTRAN language are FORTRAN IV and FORTRAN 77. In 1992, a third version, FORTRAN 90, was approved.[21,22,23,24,25]

All the languages we know and use today belong to this group. They are written in human "understandable" language. Good English speakers can easily understand the program code. This group includes languages such as Fortran, Algol, C, Pascal, Cobol, etc.

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